

DEVELOPMENT OF LOGISTICS AND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE IN OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation: This article introduces new information on the development directions of logistics and transport infrastructure in our country. In addition, consideration of the basis of development of transport logistics, determination of the essence and goals of transport logistics, as well as the impact of logistics on transport policy were considered.

Keywords: logistics, transport infrastructures, action strategy, economy, road transport, modernization, digital development, innovative logistics

INTRODUCTION

In the section of the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of our country, devoted to the priority directions of economic development and liberalization, "Deepening structural changes, increasing its competitiveness due to the modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy, free economic zones, technological parks and establishment of small industrial zones, increasing the efficiency of existing zones, organization of cluster activities, rapid development of the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, fundamentally changing the structure of the provided services, first of all, at the expense of modern high-tech types of services change, further development of logistics and road transport infrastructure, introduction of digitization methods to the economy, social sphere, management system, storage of agricultural products, tasks such as transportation and sales, further expansion of the infrastructure for providing financial and other modern market services" are listed. Based on this, today the

successful implementation of all our plans to modernize and update our country, create a new Uzbekistan, create a qualitatively new, modern structural structure of our economy, comprehensive development of our regions, and improve road transport and communication infrastructure networks. is inextricably linked to development with horses. In recent years in Uzbekistan, issues of rapid development of logistics, clusters, innovative activities, digitalization have become one of the priorities of the state economic policy. This is a full report on the digital development of Uzbekistan in order to draw a conclusion about the contribution of digitization to developing the competitiveness of our country's economy, increasing the level of human development, ensuring the employment of young people, and increasing labor productivity. A strategic state with a long-term scale requires the development of innovation policy and digitization of our economy.

In the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, it is stated "Deepening structural changes, increasing its competitiveness due to modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy, establishing free economic zones, technology parks and small industrial zones, increasing the efficiency of the existing zones, organizing the activities of clusters, rapidly developing the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, fundamentally changing the structure of the services provided, first of all, at the expense of modern high-tech types of services, logistics and Further development of rural transport infrastructure, introduction of digitization methods to the economy, social sphere, management system, storage, transportation and sale of agricultural products, financial and other modern Further expansion of the infrastructure of market services provision". Based on this, today the successful implementation of all our plans to modernize and update our country, create a new Uzbekistan, create a qualitatively new, modern structural structure of our economy, comprehensive development of our regions, and improve road transport and

communication infrastructure networks. is inextricably linked to development with horses.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATION

Currently, logistics concepts are successfully used by leading companies in the strategic and rapid management of the main areas of business. Introducing modern logistics management into business practice allows the company to find its place in the market and increase its economic stability. The use of the concept of logistics is one of the main resources for reducing the level of total costs of company resources.

The country's transport system is a set of transport enterprises and infrastructures aimed at meeting the transport needs of the economy and the population. One of the main indicators in the transport system development strategy is the transport component of the product price, which is 2-2, 5 times higher than the level of developed countries. Cost reduction in the organization of interactions between transport enterprises and other participants of the transport process is the target task of the transport system development strategy.

As the market economy develops in the country, increasing the efficiency of the transport process requires new approaches to the organization of transport. This led to the emergence of a new direction - transport logistics.

Transport, as an integral part of a large system, that is, a logistics chain, has led to the need to consider it in various aspects. In modern conditions, the transport service includes not only the supplier of goods, but also consumers, information and transaction operations, cargo transportation services, insurance, security, etc.

The study of transport from the point of view of a production enterprise cannot be limited to the sphere of material and technical relations. It should be considered in the entire logistics system - from the primary supplier to the final consumer, including intermediate stages.

Logistics potential is an integrated parameter of the logistics system, reflecting the possibilities of implementing logistics functions taking into account the factors of the external environment in which their implementation takes place. Taking into account the development of the logistics system as a result of the interaction of the factors of the micro, meso- and macro-logistic environments, it is necessary to take into account the close relations of the system elements, which have acquired not only quantitative, but also qualitative characteristics. The logistics system of the enterprise forms the material, financial and information flows at the micro level. The composition of the logistics potential at the micro level consists of the components of the internal organizational environment, which are influenced by factors specific to the immediate external environment of the organization. At the meso level, the logistics system helps enterprises and organizations to realize their goals in the processes of formation and implementation of regional and interregional economic flows, which are a combination of material (raw materials, materials), goods, financial, information, labor, energy and other flows. Therefore, the composition of the logistics potential of the region is quite wide and includes a combination of the following potentials: geographical, transport, transit, personnel, warehouse infrastructure, customs, information and communication. Each of these potentials is created taking into account the influence of the relevant group factors. The macro logistics system is not only a large material flow management system that includes regional production complexes, but also international conglomerates (corporations or financial and industrial groups), countries that have integrated the infrastructure, interstate and global flows of the economy of a particular country or group. This level of logistics capacity reflects the capabilities and resources of global transcontinental systems in minimizing overall logistics costs.

The study of the content of the concept of "logistics potential" made it possible to identify several approaches to defining the concept under consideration.

The assessment of logistics potential is required based on the development of international transit corridors, the economic attractiveness of multimodal transport and the search for optimal options for the operation of regional transport systems. The development of integrated logistics and the strengthening of the logistics market will lead to the redistribution of service tasks to companies that gather the main competences in the field of logistics.

In the future, various logistics development strategies aimed at increasing the competitiveness of regions and qualitatively changing logistics services will be implemented. Prospective directions of logistics development: further formation of the market space for logistics services; to increase the share of logistics at the local, regional, republican level, to introduce new logistics technologies to the business sector, and to form the necessary logistics capacity to reach the international level.

The purpose of the article is to consider the basis of the development of transport logistics, to determine the essence and goals of transport logistics, as well as to consider the impact of logistics on transport policy.

The cluster policy for the development of the transport industry in Uzbekistan is included in a number of national strategies, regional strategies of Central Asia, development programs, in particular, in the long-term development concept for the period up to 2040, in the transport strategy of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2035. should be reflected. It is appropriate to develop methodological recommendations for the implementation of the transit policy, the cluster policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from the point of view of the development of transit and transport-logistics potential). Effective development of cluster types is the need of the hour.

CONCLUSION

Despite many studies in this field, in our opinion, the issues of integrating the corporate information bases of transport enterprises, analyzing the behavior of transport system enterprises in competitive conditions, and systematizing the principles and approaches of the organizational and technical development of a

unified information environment for the operation of transport system enterprises are worthy of attention.

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